

Silica-Mediated Incorporation of Lipase Into The Bulk of a Deep Eutectic Solvent: An Efficient Biocatalytic Phase for Esters Synthesis

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Abstract: Aiming at sustainable solutions suitable for industrial-scale catalysis catalytic phase containing lipase and Deep Eutectic Solvent (DES) was designed. To achieve this, both physical and chemical immobilizations of lipases were performed on the surface of silica and carbon materials. The catalytic activity of developed biosystem was tested in biotransformation of α -angelica lactone into butyl levulinate at 60°C. The best results were achieved for *Candida antarctica* lipase B adsorbed on fumed silica suspended in choline chloride : glycerol (1:2) with the addition of 20 wt% of water. Under these conditions 99.9% conversion of α -angelica lactone and 100% selectivity to butyl levulinate were obtained after 45 min. The biocatalytic system maintained its activity for up to five consecutive reaction cycles with full conversion of lactone to ester. The heterogenization of the enzyme allowed the biocatalyst to be integrated into the bulk of the DES, which includes essential water. This combination resulted in the formation of a stable and easy-to-operate catalytic phase where reagents formed a second organic phase. The integration of cost-effective biocatalyst with process efficiency provides a greener alternative with significant potential for industrial use.

Introduction

Supporting studies on sustainable and ecological solutions are crucial for advancing efforts against climate change. They enable the development of innovative technologies that reduce greenhouse gas and toxic waste emissions by minimizing the environmental impact during chemical production [1, 2]. The selection of eco-friendly solvents significantly reduces harmful waste generation and supports the sustainable development of the chemical industry by minimizing environmental impact during chemical production. Chemical transformations catalyzed by enzymes offers a sustainable alternative, paving the way for efficient and eco-friendly chemical processes, leading to cleaner, greener, and safer processes that align with global sustainability goals.

In recent years, numerous studies were focused on replacing volatile organic solvents with ionic liquids as greener alternatives for biocatalysis [3, 4]. However, despite of the excellent enzyme stabilization provided by ionic liquids [5–8] only some of them are affordable as well as the toxicity issue sometimes limited their broader application. To overcome these drawbacks, the deep eutectic solvents (DESs) were used as a cheaper and greener alternative for traditional solvents. DESs are part of low transition temperature mixtures which are characterized by wide-ranging liquid state due to their negligible volatility, non-flammability, high thermal stability and often, depending on the specific compounds used in their

formulation, biodegradability. DESs are composed by hydrogen bond acceptor (HBA, e.g. quaternary ammonium salts as choline chloride) and hydrogen bond donors (HBD, e.g. alcohols as glycerol) in specific molar ratio, creating extensive intermolecular hydrogen bonding [9]. The preparation of DES is straightforward and involves mixing HBA with HBD, achieving a 100% yield using naturally derived compounds, such as urea or D-glucose.

Enzymatic processes often face challenges related to low protein thermal or chemical stability and difficulties in efficient reuse in subsequent reaction cycles. One of the most important methods for stabilization of enzyme is immobilization on a solid matrix. Additionally, the heterogenization of native protein facilitates isolation and reuse of biocatalyst after the process. The choice of matrix is crucial to maintain the enzyme in active conformation [10–12]. The most often used enzymes in the production of chemicals are lipases, which are able to catalyze esterification, hydrolysis, transesterification reactions and many other reactions [13]. Lipases achieve peak catalytic activity on hydrophobic surfaces due to their immobilization in a monomeric, open form. This phenomenon is well known as interfacial activation [14–16].

Performance of lipases in DESs as solvents or co-solvents depends on its polarity, viscosity, hydrogen bonds interactions, and water addition, what as reported causes a less ordered nanostructure of DES than its pure form [17–21]. It is well known that lipases require a water shell to maintain their active conformation, making these factors crucial in designing efficient biocatalytic system [13].

Biocatalytic systems created by the combining of the benefits of native protein immobilization with the stabilizing effects of DES on lipases was already described. Novozym 435, a commercial lipase B *Candida antarctica* (CALB) immobilized on acrylic resin was widely used as biocatalyst in DESs mediated organic reactions. Novozym 435 catalysed esterification of benzoic acid and glycerol in DES consisting of choline chloride:glycerol with 8 wt% addition of water at 60°C for 24 h, what resulted in 99% conversion of benzoic acid [22]. In other report, Novozym 435 was used for a reaction between acetic anhydride and 1-butanol carried out in DES (choline chloride:ethylene glycol) with an addition of 5 wt% of water at 60°C, and yielded 80% of butyl acetate after 24 h [23]. The same biocatalyst was applied for the synthesis of panthenyl monoacyl esters from fatty acids in various DES at 60°C. The conversion up to 83% and 100% selectivity after 6 h were achieved, and what is more, biocatalyst remained its activity through 7 cycles [24]. Novozym 435 was also used for transesterification of ethyl valerate with 1-butanol in N,N-diethylethanolammonium chloride:glycerol at 60°C for 24 h and resulted in 93% conversion of ester [25]. Transesterification of p-coumarate and 1-octanol (1:6, n:n) was performed in DES (choline chloride:urea) with 8 wt% of water added to the system at 60°C using Novozym 435. Under these conditions, 93% yield of product after 72 h was achieved [26]. In another report, this biocatalyst was employed in ultrasound assisted fatty waste oil transesterification with ethanol in DES based on choline chloride:glycerol at 59°C. Conversion of substrate reached 94% after 137 min of the reaction [27]. In all cited examples, the high impact of DES on biocatalysts was reached. High conversion of substrate and high selectivity to product formation with cost-effectiveness of DESs and low volatility and biocompatibility aligns them in the global shift towards sustainability. However, the operation with Novozym 435 is demanding causing swelling of the resin used as a support. The stability of lipase during reuse remains a significant challenge.

Only one study addresses the possibility of reusing native lipases in DES which involved combining this system with cellulose [28]. The method for recycling native enzymes in DES involved combining this system with cellulose. This approach to enzyme immobilization is

synergistically enhanced by solvent and support material, resulting in improved catalytic activity of the enzyme. In particular, the immobilization of *Candida rugosa* (CRL) lipase in the mixture of sugar-based DES (choline chloride, fructose, water 5:2:5) with nanocellulose resulted in enhance activity, efficiency and allow better thermal and pH stability in comparison to free lipase. Additionally, even after being reused more than five times, the proposed system maintained higher residual activity compared to the initial activity of free lipase. The biocatalyst maintained around 50% of its relative activity after 7 repeated cycles. However, the application of this system in organic synthesis was not presented.

α -angelica lactone biotransformation, an alternative process for the synthesis of alkyl levulinates used for the synthesis of agrochemicals, fragrances, pharmaceuticals, plasticizers, green solvents and biofuel additives was selected to test catalytic activity of the designed biocatalytic system [29]. α -angelica lactone is mainly obtained from levulinic acid, a well-known chemical derived from cellulose-rich biomass, such as agricultural residues and other lignocellulosic sources. Levulinic acid undergoes dehydration to yield α -angelica lactone making the availability of α -angelica lactone directly dependent on the large-scale production of levulinic acid [30]. Using α -angelica lactone as substrate the intramolecular condensation followed by dehydration in the presence of acidic catalyst leads to the formation of levulinic acid esters with high yields (Scheme 1) [31-34]. This approach enables to overcome obstacles related to reaction equilibrium issues of conventional esterification of levulinic acid.

Scheme 1. The proposed mechanism for the conversion of α -angelica lactone to butyl levulinate [31].

In our previous study we have demonstrated for the first time biocatalytic conversion of α -angelica lactone to levulinic acid esters in the presence of CALB immobilized on the surface of MCNTs with toluene as a solvent instead of using acidic catalyst [35].

In this work, we present a novel approach to address the challenges of stability and reuse of biocatalysts in DES by suspending lipase immobilized on silica in the bulk of DES with the addition of essential water. The catalytic performance of the created biocatalytic system was demonstrated in the biotransformation of α -angelica lactone to produce butyl levulinates and in other exemplary esterification processes.

Results and Discussion

Improving lipases performance and stability in reaction system, as well as recyclability, is crucial for the potential industry application of biocatalyst. Additionally, the use of harmless and biodegradable solvents is highly desirable to fit in with green chemistry rules and sustainable production standards [4]. The choice of the solvent or the mixture of solvents is also important factor to keep enzyme in the most active conformation. In response to these challenges, in this work the catalytic system based on immobilized CALB on solid matrix suspended in DES with low amounts of water was developed.

Preparation of heterogenous lipase-based biocatalyst

The preparation of heterogeneous biocatalysts was straightforward. The commercial carriers with various hydrophobicity, hydrophilicity, surface area, adsorption ability, and production costs were selected, such as fumed silica (SiO₂), nanosilica, multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) or activated carbon (C_(act)). As representative of lipases CALB, CRL, *Aspergillus oryzae* (AOL), and *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (PFL) were used. Water was used as solvent for immobilization. The use of phosphate buffer [36] did not affect the amount of lipase that was immobilized or the catalytic activity observed in subsequent studies. The aqueous solution of lipase was mixed with the support, at 25°C for 3 h to perform physical immobilization of lipase on the surface. Synthesized biocatalysts were analysed by TGA/DTG to calculate the lipase loading on the material (Table 1, Supporting Information, Figure S6–S13). All values of Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) surface areas S_{BET} (m²g⁻¹) of the used supports listed in Table 1 were determined by the manufacturer. The highest amount of CALB was adsorbed on fumed silica (29.0 wt%) where both well-developed specific surface area (370–420 (m²g⁻¹)) and hydrogen bonding between the carrier and lipase could influence enzyme immobilization. For nanomaterials as nanosilica and MWCNTs with similar specific surface (175–225 (m²g⁻¹)) the CALB content was 5.7 wt% and 5.1 wt% respectively. High specific surface area (1050–1150 (m²g⁻¹)) of activated carbon led to immobilization of 15.5 wt% of CALB, however the operation with activated carbon was difficult due to the dusty nature of carbon material. The loadings of other lipases were relatively low, ranging from 0.8 wt% for PFL-SiO₂ up to 6.3 wt% and 7.5 wt% for AOL-SiO₂ and CRL-SiO₂ respectively (Table 1, Supporting Information, Figure S6, S7, S14–S16).

Table 1. Characterization of heterogeneous biocatalysts.

Biocatalyst	Matrix S _{BET} (m ² g ⁻¹) ^[a]	CALB loading (wt% ±0.3) ^[b]
CALB-SiO ₂	370–420	29.0
CALB-Nanosilica	175–225	5.7
CALB-MWCNTs	233	5.1
CALB-C _(act)	1050–1150	15.5
AOL-SiO ₂	370–420	6.3
CRL-SiO ₂	370–420	7.5

PFL-SiO ₂	370–420	0.8
CALB- CH-SiO ₂	370–420	17.2

[a] SBET provided by the manufacturer. [b] Determined using TGA; the standard deviation of 3 replicate experiments.

Next, the chemical immobilization of CALB on functionalized surface of fumed silica was also performed. Firstly, the surface of silica was modified with 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane in toluene at 90°C, and subsequently modified in 10 wt% glutaraldehyde aqueous solution at room temperature. Then, the aqueous solution of CALB was mixed with glutaraldehyde activated silica at room temperature given chemically anchored lipase as biocatalyst (CALB-CH-SiO₂). 17.2 wt% of CALB was found to bound on the silica according to TGA/DTG analyses (Supporting Information, Figure S17, S18).

Based on the results, CALB-SiO₂ was chosen as the model catalyst for subsequent catalytic studies.

Designing of biocatalytic system

In the initial studies, the influence of DES on the synthesis of butyl levulinate as the model reaction in the presence of native CALB and heterogenous biocatalyst using model CALB-SiO₂ (CALB immobilized on fumed silica) was tested (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2. Conversion of α-angelica lactone to butyl levulinate.

According to the literature, choline chloride – based DESs are commonly used to increase effectiveness of lipases in various chemical processes [17–21]. For that reason, DESs were synthesized using choline chloride (ChCl, 1 mol equiv) as HBA and glycerol, ethylene glycol or urea (Gly, EG, U, 2 mol equiv), or glucose (Glu, 0.5 mol equiv) as HBD. The reagents were mixed with heating and next dried under vacuum. The amount of water in synthesized DESs was analyzed (Table 2).

Table 2. The amount of water in synthesized DESs.

DES	Water content (wt% ±0.02) ^[a]
ChCl:Gly (1:2)	0.56
ChCl:EG (1:2)	1.06
ChCl:U (1:2)	0.98
ChCl:Glu (2:1)	1.31

[a] Determined using Karl-Fischer analysis; water content in toluene 0.02 wt%; the standard deviation of 3 replicate experiments.

DESs were tested independently or as co-solvents with toluene as potential stabilizers of CALB or CALB-SiO₂ in biotransformation of α -angelica lactone (Figure 1). In all cases, a certain amount of water from the DES, toluene, and native lipase is present in the reaction system to ensure a water shell that maintains the lipase in its active conformation. In case of heterogenous catalyst CALB-SiO₂ the reaction system was consisting of two phases: catalytic phase with CALB-SiO₂ suspended in DES and organic phase with substrate and the product. In the case of the native enzyme, it was not possible to homogenize the enzyme with DES.

The selectivity of biotransformation to butyl levulinate was determined by GC and reached almost 100% (<99.9%) for all presented experiments. No additional products were identified which are postulated in acidic catalyzed version of this reaction. Using Amberlyst 36 [33] or a range of choline-exchanged heteropolyacids [34] as catalysts at 75°C led to the formation of levulinic acid esters with 79-94% selectivity and full conversion of α -angelica. The identified by-product was the unreacted intermediate, pseudo-butyl levulinate.

Immobilized CALB-SiO₂ resulted in improved performance (Figure 1). Native lipase was able to convert only 76% of α -angelica lactone in 90 min, while full conversion was noticed for CALB-SiO₂ after 90 min of reaction carried out in toluene. The reaction system was efficient but the recovery and reuse of CALB was unsuccessful. The full conversion of α -angelica lactone in the presence of CALB-SiO₂ suspended in toluene (90 min) as well as in the mixture of toluene and ChCl:Gly (1:2) (120 min) was observed. Anyway, using ChCl:Gly (1:2) DES alone high conversion 95.4% after 180 min was also obtained. This slight variation in conversion values presumably results from higher viscosity of DES that prolonged reaction time. Taking into the consideration various DES compositions with toluene, glycerol-based DES was the most active dispersion medium for CALB-SiO₂ in the tested reaction. The highest viscosity observed for ChCl:Glu (2:1) influenced on the slight lowering of the conversion value (93.2%) after 240 min [37]. The lowest conversions of α -angelica lactone were achieved for the reaction in toluene with ChCl:U (1:2) (51.9%, 240 min) and ChCl:EG (1:2) (20.4%, 240 min). Glycerol and glucose are well-known stabilizing agents for lipases, whereas urea and ethylene glycol are known to have a denaturing effect on enzymes. The obtained results fit to those reported in the literature [38–41]. A control experiment without the enzyme was conducted, and the α -angelica lactone remained unreacted.

Figure 1. The influence of solvent mixture on α -angelica lactone conversion in the presence of CALB-SiO₂. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, toluene, ChCl:Gly (1:2) or mixture (M) of DES (ChCl:Gly (1:2), ChCl:Glu (2:1), ChCl:U (1:2), ChCl:EG (1:2))

with toluene (1:4, v:v) 1 mL, 75 mg CALB-SiO₂ or 21.8 mg of native CALB, 60°C, 250 rpm; conversion determined using GC.

Water addition

Encouraged by very promising results obtained in the presence of ChCl:Gly (1:2) and CALB-SiO₂, the water addition effect to DES in the range of 5 – 20 wt% was checked. The main goal of the study was to decrease viscosity of DES to improve free transfer of reagents to and from catalytic center of enzyme, to enhance α -angelica lactone conversion. It was reported that adding water has a glue-like effect, causing the solvation of DES components. However, when the water content in DES exceeds 35 wt%, it disrupts the structure [42]. Moreover, the presence of water significantly helps to stabilize the active three-dimensional conformation of the enzyme [14–16]. The effect of water addition was observed for native CALB in esterification of oleic acid and decanol in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/10 wt% H₂O at 45°C what allowed to achieve 98% yield of ester [43]. In other studies, Novozyme 435 in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/8 wt% H₂O was used for effective monobenzoate glycerol synthesis with 99% yield [44].

Increasing of water content in ChCl:Gly (1:2) DES influenced better CALB-SiO₂ performance and α -angelica lactone conversion (Figure 2). The best result was observed for the use of ChCl:Gly (1:2) solution with 20 wt% of water (ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O) with full conversion of α -angelica (99.9%) lactone after 45 min, that was even better than for the use of toluene (full conversion 99.9 % after 90 min). On the other hand, the presence of water could induce the hydrolysis of the newly formed ester, converting it back into levulinic acid. However, the GC analysis of butyl levulinate in the samples taken from the post-reaction mixtures, carried out in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O and toluene, revealed 99.9% yield of the ester. The analysis confirms that, once formed, butyl levulinate does not undergo subsequent hydrolysis back to levulinic acid and can be obtained in near-quantitative yields under the developed conditions, with hydrolysis of ester occurring at negligible levels within the detectable range.

Figure 2. The influence of water addition to ChCl:Gly (1:2) on α -angelica lactone conversion in the presence of CALB-SiO₂. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2) 0 – 20 wt% H₂O or toluene 1 mL, CALB-SiO₂ 75 mg, 60°C, 250 rpm; conversion determined using GC.

The visualization of biocatalytic system based on silica CALB-SiO₂ suspended in DES, e.g. 20 wt% of water (ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O) was presented in Figure 3. The idea of the performance of CALB-SiO₂ in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O was illustrated on Scheme 2. First,

the immobilization of CALB on the surface of silica enabled the enzyme to enter the bulk of DES with the essential water, resulting in the creation of a stable and easy-to-operate catalytic phase (Scheme 3). Next, the reagents are added, creating a second organic phase. After stirring the biphasic system, the reaction proceeds efficiently. Upon completion, toluene is added to facilitate the quantitative isolation of the product. The catalytic phase can be then directed to the next reaction cycle. The results of the recycle tests of catalytic phase (Table 4) are described after the determination of key reaction parameters.

Scheme 3. System for biotransformation of α -angelica lactone to butyl levulinate in the presence of designed biocatalytic system.

Key reaction parameters

Subsequently, the following key reaction parameters were studied: the influence of DES amount, the molar ratio of α -angelica lactone to alcohol, the amount of biocatalyst, temperature, and the type of lipase and support on α -angelica lactone biotransformation. Studies of the influence of DES amount showed that (Supporting Information, Figure S19) higher amounts of ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O than 1.5 mL per 1 mmol of α -angelica used for

the process resulted retardation of reaction due to the lower concentration of reagents. Conversely, using less than 1.0 mL of ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O caused problem with mixing of reaction system with heterogeneous CALB-SiO₂. The influence of molar ratio of the α -angelica lactone to 1-butanol on the catalytic performance of catalyst revealed (Supporting Information, Figure S20) that 2-fold molar excess of 1-butanol results in full conversion of α -angelica lactone in 45 min. Further increasing of the molar excess of 1-butanol did not impact the conversion, while using 1-butanol in equimolar amounts was not sufficient.

Full conversion of α -angelica lactone was reached in the presence of various amounts of CALB-SiO₂ between 50-100 mg (Figure 4). However, lowering of biocatalyst amount to 50 mg caused decreased of reaction rate, (full conversion of α -angelica lactone after 90 min). The use of 30 mg of biocatalyst resulted in 89% conversion in 90 min. These results confirm high activity of developed CALB-SiO₂ suspended in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O biocatalytic system.

Figure 4. The influence of CALB-SiO₂ amount on α -angelica lactone conversion in the presence of CALB-SiO₂. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, CALB-SiO₂ 30 – 100 mg, 60°C, 250 rpm; conversion determined using GC.

Figure 5. The influence of temperature on α -angelica lactone conversion in the presence of CALB-SiO₂. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, CALB-SiO₂ 75 mg, 30 – 60°C, 250 rpm; conversion determined using GC.

The influence of temperature on CALB-SiO₂ performance in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O in α -angelica lactone conversion was also studied (Figure 5). The highest reaction rate was reached at 60°C probably due to decreasing of viscosity of DES, what in turn enhanced lipase

performance. It is worth highlighting that a relatively low temperature for this reaction (30°C) also enabled the full conversion of α -angelica lactone to butyl levulinate, but in 120 minutes. Taking into consideration solvent modification from toluene to ChCl:Gly (1:2), experiments with other physically immobilized on fumed silica lipases, such as: AOL, CRL and PFL were performed (Figure 6; Supporting Information, Figure S21). The amount of each heterogeneous biocatalyst was calculated to reach the same theoretical amount of lipase in each experiment for comparison reason (21.8 mg of lipase per 1 mmol of α -angelica lactone). For immobilized PFL the amount of biocatalyst corresponds to the maximum capacity of siliceous material in DES. The maximum capacity, which resulted in efficient mixing of the reaction mixture, was observed at 400 mg of heterogeneous biocatalyst based on fumed silica. The exceeding of this value contributed to poor mixing. All developed heterogenous catalysts were active in the tested reaction, however the activity was superior for CALB-SiO₂ (full conversion of α -angelica lactone after 45 min). Lipase from LAO-SiO₂ caused full conversion of substrate after 60 min. The activity of lipases from CRL-SiO₂ and PFL-SiO₂ were slightly lower (88% and 75.3% of conversions of α -angelica lactone after 60 min).

Figure 6. The influence of lipase type on α -angelica lactone conversion in the presence of CALB-SiO₂. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, 21.8 mg of immobilized lipase (CALB-SiO₂ 75 mg, *Aspergillus oryzae*-SiO₂ 346 mg, *Candida rugosa*-SiO₂ 291 mg, *Pseudomonas fluorescens*-SiO₂ 400 mg) 60°C, 250 rpm; conversion determined using GC.

Table 3. The influence of type of the support for CALB on α -angelica lactone conversion.

Biocatalyst	Conversion of α -angelica lactone (%) ^[a]	Activity ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$)	Specific activity ($\mu\text{molmg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$)	Activity recovery (%) ^[b]
CALB (native)	99.9 (60 min)	15.8	0.7	–
CALB-SiO ₂	99.9 (45 min)	22.6	1.0	143
CALB-Nanosilica	99.9 (90 min)	11.2	0.5	71

CALB-MWCNTs	99.9 (90 min)	11.5	0.5	73
CALB-C _(act)	99.9 (120 min)	8.4	0.4	53

[a] Determined using GC; standard deviation 2.0%. [b] Activity recovery=(activity of immobilized enzyme/activity of native enzyme)×100%. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, 21.8 mg of immobilized or native CALB (CALB-SiO₂ 75 mg, CALB-Nanosilica 382 mg, CALB-MWCNTs 427 mg, CALB-C(act) 141 mg) 60°C, 250 rpm.

It is known that the choice of proper support for enzyme immobilization is crucial for its stabilization, maintaining active conformation and recycling [10–12]. For this purpose the effect of the type of support for CALB activity in biotransformation of α -angelica lactone performed in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O was studied (Table 3; Supporting Information, Figure S22, S23). The amount of each heterogeneous biocatalyst was calculated to 21.8 mg of lipase per 1 mmol of α -angelica lactone based on TGA/DTG analyses, and the wt% of CALB immobilized on fumed silica, nanosilica, multiwalled carbon nanotubes and activated carbon was presented in Table 3.

The highest amount of CALB was incorporated into fumed silica (29.0 wt%) due to hydrogen bonding between the carrier and the lipase, which facilitated enzyme immobilization. Activated carbon immobilized 15.5 wt% of CALB. For nanomaterials such as nanosilica and MWCNTs, the CALB content was 5.7 wt% and 5.1 wt%, respectively. The best catalytic activity was achieved for CALB-SiO₂, furthermore lipase physical immobilization on silica maintained its activity by 143% in comparison to native form. Full α -angelica lactone conversion in reaction using CALB-Nanosilica and CALB-MWCNTs was observed after 90 min, and for CALB-C(act) after 120 min. Immobilization of CALB on these supports caused lowering in the activity of lipase by 71%, 73% and even 53%, respectively, in comparison to native form. According to the literature, lipases exhibit the highest activity when immobilized on a hydrophobic matrix. Moreover, hydrophilic surfaces are often modified to maintain hydrophobic properties [14–16]. The experiments conducted here demonstrated that additional costly surface modifications are not necessary. Significant synergistic action of the extended hydrogen network formed between the fumed silica support, lipase, and DES stabilizes CALB in its active conformation, thereby enhancing its activity.

Recycling test

Moving forward, the influence of immobilization method, physical or chemical, on CALB activity in biotransformation of α -angelica lactone was examined (Table 3). The influence of immobilization as well as the solvent choice were crucial for CALB performance and stability in α -angelica lactone biotransformation. Immobilization of native lipase on silica facilitated easy biocatalyst recycling by permitting its suspension in ChCl:Gly (1:2).

After each reaction cycle the post reaction mixture was washed with toluene to extract all reagents and the GC analysis of DES conformed the purity of catalytic phase (Supporting Information, Figure S24). The biocatalyst remained in the DES, making its removal unnecessary and creating a catalytic phase that could be easily recycled.

Table 4. The influence of CALB immobilization method on α -angelica lactone conversion and recyclability of biocatalytic system.

Enzyme form	Solvent	Conversion (%) ^[a] after 1 st cycle, 30°C (Activity ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$))	Conversion (%) ^[a] after 3 rd cycle, 30°C (Activity ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$))	Conversion (%) ^[a] after 1 st cycle, 60°C (Activity ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$))	Conversion (%) ^[a] after 3 rd cycle, 60°C (Activity ($\mu\text{mol min}^{-1}$))
Native	Toluene	99.9 (180 min) (5.5)	–	78.8 (90 min) (8.7)	–
Native	ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H ₂ O	99.9 (180 min) (5.5)	–	99.9 (90 min) (15.8)	–
Physical immobilization	Toluene	99.9 (180 min) (5.6)	74.2 (180 min) (4.1)	99.9 (90 min) (15.7)	58.0 (90 min) (6.4)
Physical immobilization	ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H ₂ O	99.9 (180 min) (5.6)	99.9 (180 min) ^[b] (5.6) 86.6 (180 min) ^[c] (4.8)	99.9 (45 min) (22.8)	91.6 (45 min) (20.4)
Chemical immobilization	Toluene	99.9 (180 min) (5.5)	66.8 (180 min) (3.7)	99.9 (90 min) (15.7)	54.1 (45 min) (12.0)
Chemical immobilization	ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H ₂ O	99.9 (180 min) (5.6)	90.4 (180 min) (5.0)	99.9 (45 min) (22.8)	83.6 (45 min) (18.6)

[a] Conversion of α -angelica lactone determined using GC; standard deviation 2.0%. [b] Conversion after 5 cycles; [c] conversion after 6 cycles. Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, 21.8 mg of immobilized or native CALB (CALB-SiO₂ 75 mg (physical), CALB-SiO₂ 128 mg (chemical)), 30°C or 60°C, 250 rpm.

The main differences between activity of CALB immobilized physically or chemically on silica in DES was noticed during recycling tests. It is known that chemical bonding may reduce activity of immobilized proteins [45] what was observed after 3rd cycle in comparison to biocatalyst with physically embedded CALB (Table 4). This effect was more visible at 30°C where the conversion drop was observed only for chemically grafted enzyme, from 99.9% after 1st cycle to 90.4% after 3rd cycle. The results at 60°C showed similar tendency but here the protein deactivation in higher temperature also resulted in slightly lower conversion of α -angelica lactone for physically immobilized CALB, from 99.9% after 1st cycle to 91.6% after 3rd cycle, and for chemically immobilized CALB, from 99.9% after 1st cycle to 83.6% after 3rd cycle.

The selection of the reaction medium significantly influenced CALB stability during recycling studies and its resistance to high temperatures. Switching the solvent from toluene to ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O significantly improved the activity and stability of the native protein in the studied process. While at 30°C the conversion values and reaction times were the same (99.9%, 180 min), differences were noticeable at higher temperature, with 78.8% (90 min) for toluene and 99.9% (90 min) for DES. For the immobilized enzyme, differences in performance in toluene and ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O were observed only during recycling tests. For instance, physically immobilized CALB maintained its high stability in DES for up to 5 reaction

cycles at 30°C (99.9%, 180 min) and dropped to 86.6% after 6th cycle caused by protein deactivation. When carried out the reaction in toluene, the conversion dropped to 74.2% (30°C) or 58.0% (60°C) after 3 cycles.

Method versatility

The biotransformation of α -angelica lactone with other alcohols, including methanol, ethanol, propanol was tested (Table 5). For all listed above alcohols, the conversion of α -angelica lactone reached 99.9% after 45 min at 60°C. Additionally, the activity of biocatalytic system was tested in the esterification of furfuryl alcohol with octanoic acid, and the esterification of oleic acid with methanol. Obtained results, presented in the Table 4 and Supporting Information Figure S4, S5, showed significant potential of designed CALB-SiO₂ suspended in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O in esterification reactions.

Table 5. Versatility of reaction system with CALB-SiO₂ biocatalyst suspended in DES.

Reagent 1	Reagent 2	Product	Time	Conversion of reagent 1 (%) ^[a]
	45 (min)	99.9 ^[b]		
		45 (min)	99.9 ^[b]	
		45 (min)	99.9 ^[b]	
		45 (min)	99.9 ^[b]	
	24 (h)	93.8 ^[c]		
	24 (h)	86.3 ^[d]		

[a] Determined using GC, standard deviation 2.0%. [b] Reaction conditions: α -angelica lactone 1.0 mmol, 1-butanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, 75 mg CALB-SiO₂, 60°C, 250 rpm. [c] Reaction conditions: furfuryl alcohol 1.0 mmol, octanoic acid 3.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, 75 mg CALB-SiO₂, 60°C, 250 rpm. [d] Reaction conditions: oleic acid 1.0 mmol, methanol 2.0 mmol, ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O 1 mL, 75 mg CALB-SiO₂, 60°C, 250 rpm.

Comparison with existing methods

To emphasize the advancements and innovations of the biocatalytic system developed in this study, a comparison with existing methods was conducted. In general, levulinate esters can be obtained directly from polysaccharides (cellulose) [46, 47], monosaccharides (glucose or fructose) [47, 48], levulinic acid [49] or its precursors as furfuryl alcohol [50] in the presence of acidic catalysts and only one work reported biocatalytic method [35]. However, methods utilizing α -angelica lactone as a substrate resulted in the formation of levulinic esters with high yields [31-35, 51-55]. This approach effectively overcomes the challenges associated with the reaction equilibrium in conventional esterification.

Previously, DES based on choline chloride and acidic compound para-toluene sulfonic acid was also used as a highly active acidic catalyst to produce levulinate esters. The conversion of levulinic acid achieved 99.8% at 80°C in 1 h with 99.9% selectivity to ethyl levulinate [56]. In other studies, furfuryl alcohol was transformed to ethyl levulinate in the presence of DES composed of choline chloride and ethanol with the addition of 5-sulfonic salicylic acid. After 2 h of reaction at 110°C, full conversion of furfuryl alcohol and approximately 90% yield of ethyl levulinate were observed [57]. Ethyl levulinate was also synthesized from delignified sugarcane bagasse using photoactive ternary acidic deep eutectic solvents formed by choline chloride, citric acid and FeCl₃ under MW-xenon irradiation in 90 min with 79.1% yield [58]. Table 6 presents a comparison of literature data for the synthesis of butyl levulinate.

Table 6. Comparison existing methods of butyl levulinate synthesis.

Entry	Catalyst	Reaction conditions	Reaction parameters ^[a]	Lit.
1	Amberlyst 36 (0.05 wt%)	α -angelica lactone : butanol (1:1, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 75°C, 240 min	Full conversion, selectivity	94% [33]
2	Choline-based heteropoly acid (20 wt%) Ch ₂ H ₄ P ₂ W ₁₈ O ₆₂	α -angelica lactone : butanol (1:1, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 75°C, 60 min	Full conversion, selectivity, reused 5 times	79.4% [34]
3	WO ₃ immobilized on ZrO ₂ (0.75 wt% of active phase)	α -angelica lactone : butanol (1:1, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 75°C, 360 min	Full conversion, selectivity	43% [51]
4	Nb ₂ O ₅ nanoparticles (18 wt%)	0.33 M α -angelica lactone in ethanol, neat, 110°C, 180 min	Full conversion, selectivity, reused 3 times	99% [52]
5	HClO ₄ immobilized on SiO ₂ (1.1 wt% of active phase)	α -angelica lactone : butanol (1:43, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 90°C, 120 min	94% yield	[53]
6	PTA immobilized on HAC-600 (5 wt% of active phase) ^[b]	α -angelica lactone : butanol (1:11, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 150°C, 450 min	88% yield	[54]
7	[C ₂ mim][OTf]-Al(OTf) ₃ , $\chi_{\text{Al(OTf)}_3} = 0.25$ immobilized on MWCNTs (0.03 wt% of active phase)	α -angelica lactone : butanol (1:1, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 60°C, 60 min	Full conversion, selectivity, reused 6 times	99% [31]

8	[C ₂ mim][OTf]-Al(OTf) ₃ , χ _{Al(OTf)₃} = 0.25 immobilized on UIO-67 (7.8 wt% of active phase) ^[c]	α-angelica lactone : butanol (1:1, <i>n/n</i>), neat, 70°C, 90 min	Full conversion, 99% selectivity, reused 5 times	[55]
9	CALB immobilized on MWCNTs-PTFE (35 wt% of active phase)	α-angelica lactone : butanol (1:2, <i>n/n</i>), 1 mL toluene, 20°C, 120 min	99% conversion, 100% selectivity, reused 6 times	[35]
10	CALB immobilized on SiO ₂ (20 wt% of active phase)	α-angelica lactone : butanol (1:2, <i>n/n</i>), 1 mL ChCl:Gly (1:2)/ 20 wt% H ₂ O, 30°C, 180 min	99.9% conversion, 100% selectivity, reused 6 times	This work

[a] Conversion of α-angelica lactone; selectivity to butyl levulinate. [b] PTA: phosphotungstic acid; HAC humin-derived activated carbon. [c] UIO-67: metal-organic framework.

The use of acidic catalysts, such as Amberlyst 36, choline-based heteropoly acid Ch₂H₄P₂W₁₈O₆₂ and WO₃ immobilized on ZrO₂ resulted in full conversion of α-angelica lactone at 75°C and lower yields of butyl levulinate (94% (240 min), 79% (60 min) and 43% (360 min), respectively) due to the formation of pseudo butyl levulinate or levulinic acid as by-products [33, 34, 51]. For the heteropoly acid-based catalyst, five cycles of the reaction with reused catalyst were performed, and a decrease to 69.9% yield was observed in the 5th run [51]. Full conversion of α-angelica lactone with 99% selectivity to butyl levulinate at 110°C in 180 min in the presence of Nb₂O₅ nanoparticles was reported with two effective cycles of catalyst [52]. Perchloric acid supported on silica gel was also tested for esterification with 94% yield of ester formation at 90°C after 120 min [53]. Next, phosphotungstic acid (PTA) embedded on humin-derived activated carbon (HAC) was used to produce butyl levulinate with 88% yield at 150°C over 450 min. During the catalyst recycling test, a slight decrease in yield was observed, dropping from 87% to 76% in the 5th cycle [54]. Next investigations revealed that acidic imidazolium-based ionic liquids modified with Al(OTf)₃ immobilized on multiwalled carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs) catalyzed α-angelica lactone transformation to butyl levulinate with full conversion and 99% selectivity at 60°C in 60 min. The catalyst remained stable through five reaction cycles, after which the conversion dropped to 98% and the selectivity decreased from 99% to 94% [31]. In other studies, the same catalytic ionic liquid active phase supported on metal-organic framework UIO-67 showed as well high catalytic performance with full conversion of α-angelica lactone and 99% selectivity with activity in five reaction cycles [55]. Finally, the use of CALB immobilized on the surface of Teflon-modified MWCNTs, instead of a metal-based acidic catalyst, revealed that mild reaction conditions, such as temperature (20°C) and a short reaction time (120 min) are sufficient to achieve 99% conversion of α-angelica lactone with 100% selectivity with possibility of six effective cycles of catalyst. The drawbacks of this method, in comparison to the described in this work, are the necessity of the modification of the surface of enzyme carrier with Teflon what generate the addition step for the synthesis of biocatalyst and the use of toluene as a solvent [35].

Conclusion

This work focuses on advancing methods to enhance the stability and recyclability of lipases for fine chemical synthesis, a persistent challenge in biocatalysis. To tackle these challenges, the study explores the use of DESs to stabilize enzymes in their active form.

The creation of catalytic phase containing DES and the enzyme, which would be easy to handle and recycle, while maintaining the activity and stability of enzyme was not trivial. It was

challenging to dissolve or suspend native lipases directly in DES. Therefore, silica as a mediator to incorporate the lipase into the bulk of DES was proposed. Designed biocatalytic system consisting of CALB physically immobilized on fumed silica suspended in ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O showed high activity in biotransformation of α -angelica lactone into alkyl levulinates reaching 100% selectivity and 99.9% conversion in 45min. Moreover, presented biosystem indicated its activity in esterification reactions, such as between furfuryl alcohol and octanoic acid, and between oleic acid and methanol. It reveals great potential to be implemented in many others reactions from organic synthesis sector.

In summary, the results of this work ensure a balance between a highly active, stable, recyclable, and biodegradable catalyst. This method is proposed as a generic approach to green chemistry dedicated to support biocatalytic synthesis of value-added chemicals. Dynamic simulations of the designed system to verify experimental findings and advance our understanding in this area will be performed in our group.

Experimental Section

Materials and methods

All DES components: choline chloride ($\geq 99\%$), glycerol ($>99\%$), urea ($\geq 99\%$), glucose ($>99.5\%$), ethylene glycol (99.8%), lipases as: native lipase B from *Candida antarctica* in aqueous-glycerol solution (activity ≥ 5000 (LUg⁻¹)), lyophilized lipase from *Candida rugosa* (activity ≥ 700 (Umg⁻¹)), lyophilized amano lipase from *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (activity ≥ 20000 (Ug⁻¹)), native lipase from *Aspergillus oryzae* in aqueous-glycerol (activity ≥ 100000 (Ug⁻¹)), the supports: fumed silica (99.8%; SBET=370-420 (m²g⁻¹)), activated carbon SBET=1050–1150 (m²g⁻¹), nanosilica (99.8%; SBET=175–225 (m²g⁻¹)), and reagents such as: α -angelica lactone (98%), 1-butanol (99.9%), propanol (99.9%), ethanol (96%), methanol (99.8%), toluene (99.8%), oleic acid (90%), octanoic acid (99.0%), furfuryl alcohol ($\geq 98\%$), 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (99%), 25% aqueous solution of glutaraldehyde and toluene (0.02 wt% water) were supplied by Sigma-Aldrich (Merck Group, Poland). Industrial grade multiwalled carbon nanotubes MWCNTs (SBET=233 (m²g⁻¹)) were purchased from Cheap Tubes Inc (USA). Gas chromatography (GC) analyses were performed to monitor the reactions progress. GC were taken on a SHIMADZU GC-2010 Plus equipped with a Zebtron ZB-5MSi column (30 m \times 0.32 mm; 0.25 μ m) and the conversion of α -angelica lactone was measured using calibration method with decan as an internal standard. TG/DTG analyses of all supports and biocatalysts were determined using the TGA/DTG 851 Mettler-Toledo thermogravimeter (25°C – 800°C, heating rate of 10°Cmin⁻¹, nitrogen flow 60 mLmin⁻¹). ¹H NMR (400 MHz) and ¹³C NMR (101 MHz) spectra of butyl levulinate was recorded on a Varian system. Specific surface areas (SBET) of used supports were provided according to the material specification listed by the manufacturer. The water content in DESs and toluene was determined through volumetric Karl Fischer titration using a Metrohm 915 KF Ti-Touch instrument (Metrohm, Herisau) equipped with HYDRANAL™ – Titrant 5 and HYDRANAL™ – Solvent from Merck KGaA.

ChCl-based DES preparation

Choline chloride – based DES were synthesized according to the literature reports with some modifications in a scale of 10 g: Choline chloride (ChCl, 1 mol equiv) as HBA and glycerol, ethylene glycol or urea (Gly, EG, U, 2 mol equiv), or glucose (Glu, 0.5 mol equiv) as HBD were mixed in a 50 mL round-bottomed flask with heating at 80°C for 1 h until a homogeneous viscous solution was formed. The obtained DESs (ChCl:Gly (1:2), ChCl:U (1:2), ChCl:EG (1:2), ChCl:Glu (2:1)) were dried under the vacuum using a Schlenk line (40°C, 24 h) and the amount of water was determined using Karl-Fischer method (ChCl:Gly (1:2) 0.56 wt% H₂O, ChCl:U (1:2)

0.98 wt% H₂O, ChCl:EG (1:2) 1.06 wt% H₂O, ChCl:Glu (2:1) 1.31 wt% H₂O). DESs were used without further purification or after the addition of 20 wt% of water (ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O).

Physical immobilization of lipase, preparation of CALB-SiO₂, AOL-SiO₂, CRL-SiO₂, PFL-SiO₂
Fumed silica (100 mg), native lipase CALB, lipase from *Aspergillus oryzae*, *Candida rugosa* or *Pseudomonas fluorescens* (0.7 g) and 1.5 mL of deionized water were stirred in a 25 mL round-bottom flask in a thermostatic shaker (250 rpm) at 20°C for 3 h. Then, biocatalyst was filtered off, washed with deionized water (3 × 10 mL) and dried under the vacuum using a Schlenk line (25°C, 24 h).

Chemical immobilization of lipase, preparation of CALB-CH-SiO₂

CALB was chemically anchored to fumed silica according to the literature reports with some modifications: Fumed silica (1 g), 3-aminopropyltriethoxysilane (3 mL) and toluene (10 mL) were mixed in a 50 mL round-bottomed flask with heating at 90°C for 24 h. Then, the material was filtered off, washed with toluene (3 × 5 mL) and dried under the vacuum using a Schlenk line (25°C, 24 h). After that, prepared material was mixed with 10 wt% aqueous solution of glutaraldehyde in a 50 mL round-bottomed flask at room temperature for 24 h. Next, modified with glutaraldehyde material was filtered off, washed with deionized water (3 × 10 mL) and dried under the vacuum using a Schlenk line (25°C, 24 h). Finally, native solution of CALB (7 g), glutaraldehyde activated silica material (1 g) and 15 mL of deionized water were stirred in a 50 mL round-bottom flask in a thermostatic shaker (250 rpm) at 20°C for 3 h. Biocatalyst was filtered off, washed with deionized water (3 × 20 mL) and dried under the vacuum on the Schlenk line (25°C, 24 h).

General procedure of butyl levulinate synthesis from α -angelica lactone

In a 15 mL vial, α -angelica lactone (1.0 mmol), 1-butanol (2.0 mmol), ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O (1 mL) were mixed, and then 75 mg of CALB-SiO₂ were added. The reaction was performed at 60°C and stirred in a thermostatic shaker (250 rpm) for 45 min. Reaction progress was monitored by GC (Supporting Information, Figure S1). After the reaction, 2 mL of toluene was added in to the two-phase system comprised of: CALB-SiO₂ suspended in solution of ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O and the organic layer with product and unreacted 1-butanol. The catalytic phase was isolated and washed two times with 2 mL of toluene to regain the rest of organic compounds. Next, the solvent and 1-butanol were distilled off, and obtained butyl levulinate (yield 99%) was analysed using ¹H and ¹³C NMR (Supporting Information, Figure S2, S3).

Biocatalyst recycling

The catalytic phase was dried under the vacuum using a Schlenk line (2 h, 20°C) and reused.

General procedure of esterification of furfuryl alcohol and octanoic acid

In a 15 mL vial, furfuryl alcohol (1.0 mmol), octanoic acid (3.0 mmol), ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O (1 mL) were mixed, and then 75 mg of CALB-SiO₂ was added. The reaction mixture was stirred (250 rpm) in a thermostatic shaker at 60°C for 24 h. Reaction progress was monitored by GC (Supporting Information, Figure S4).

General procedure of esterification of methanol and oleic acid

In a 15 mL vial, oleic acid (1.0 mmol), methanol (2.0 mmol), ChCl:Gly (1:2)/20 wt% H₂O (1 mL) were mixed, and then 75 mg of CALB-SiO₂ was added. The reaction mixture was stirred (250 rpm) in a thermostatic shaker at 60°C for 24 h. Reaction progress was monitored by GC (Supporting Information, Figure S5).

Statistical analysis

The conversion of substrate and selectivity to product were determined using GC. All samples were collected with syringe (0.03 mL) and dissolved in acetonitrile. Each sample was analysed 3 times, the standard deviation \pm 2.0%. The values presented in the figures and tables is an average of three independent experiments.

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.

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